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A Phenomenological Analysis of Mathematics Teachers' Experiences of Transitioning to Fully Online Teaching: A Case of Three Filipino Teachers

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic brought along the implementation of health protocols including physical distancing measures that intended to stem the tide of viral transmission across the globe. This constraint and the pressure put upon educational systems to ensure continuity of learning have forced schools to abandon face-to-face classes and utilize alternative teaching methods for the foreseeable future. The purpose of this study was to illustrate the emergency remote teaching of mathematics in the Philippines during the early onset of the pandemic from the perspective of mathematics teachers in their attempts to ensure continuous delivery of instruction. The study utilized a phenomenological research design in which online written interviews were conducted with three teacher-respondents. Google Docs was used, wherein questions and responses were posted asynchronously. Content analysis was used to analyze the textual data using spreadsheet software, and communication was supported by online tools such as Google Meet. Moreover, the ideas of studying, teacher acts, and didactic transposition as borrowed from Chevallard's Anthropological Theory of Didactics were utilized as lenses for analysis. The study found that the respondents' stories of transitioning online in the middle of an unprecedented crisis were replete with both challenges and opportunities. Specifically, institutional preferences leaned towards online teaching, with the abrupt shift posing issues on maintaining quality mathematics teaching and learning while reducing mathematical content, establishing digital rapport with students, and simplifying assessment methods. On the other hand, the respondents shared hopeful reflections on the opportunities that came with the shift, such as thinking about what truly matters in mathematics education and discovering the online teaching-learning setup.

Keywords: Anthropological Theory of Didactics, online mathematics teaching, phenomenology

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 cast a predicament on different levels of societies around the world — from individual to institutional, and national to global, with effects that would ripple for the years to come. Efforts to mitigate the spread of the disease were deemed disruptive to the social order since they entailed distancing measures. Such brought about an unprecedented disruption in many facets of human life, in which education was no exception. In education systems worldwide, school closures across countries affected almost 1.5 billion learners prior to reopening in late April (UNESCO, 2020a). Findings from a report based on the joint survey of The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) and The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) revealed that the pandemic necessitated teachers, principals, and students worldwide to adapt to alternative teaching and learning methods (Rožman et al., 2022) given

that physical classes were not an option due to the imminent health hazards these bring.

Bennett (2020) aptly described the educational situation as a tectonic shift that entailed an abrupt transition from face-to-face (F2F) to distance learning, regardless of its form (e.g., online, television, radio). Moreover, teachers and students were suddenly conducting and participating in distance learning to minimize disruptions, notwithstanding their readiness and willingness to embrace such media (Inside Higher Ed & Hanover Research, 2020; Young, 2020).

Emergency Remote Teaching

Hodges et al. (2020) noted the emergence of the term emergency remote teaching (ERT) that described the situation education stakeholders faced during the pandemic. They defined ERT as “a temporary shift of instructional delivery to an alternate delivery mode due to crisis circumstances”. In this regard, based on Dahya's (2016) report, ERT can be classified under “education in emergencies,

conflict, and protracted crisis” (p. 9) and may have an impact on social stability and access to quality education. Moreover, UNESCO (2020b) reported that the quick shift to online learning as means of ERT had been challenging even for teachers in countries well-equipped with information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure. This is primarily because effective online education requires careful and systematic planning and design (Hodges et al., 2020).

The Philippine Educational Interruption

In response to the growing number of infections, the Philippine government declared a state of public health emergency near the middle of March 2020 (Office of the President, 2020), and subsequently implemented the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) across provinces and cities in attempts to control and contain the spread of COVID-19. The Department of Education (2020) ordered school closures in both public and private schools that began 10 March 2020, although some private institutions had already suspended classes prior to the order.

At the onset of the pandemic, schools in the Philippines were following different school calendars. This was a result of the transition from a 10-year basic education system to a global standard of K to 12 initiated in 2012 (Sarvi et al., 2015). In schools that opted not to abruptly finish the school year, the primary means of ERT was to teach online. Schools conducted either synchronous or asynchronous classes, or a mix of both. For synchronous classes, the teaching-learning activity was held real-time through videoconferencing. Meanwhile, learners did online activities at their own pace within a certain time frame in asynchronous classes. However, this shift was met with resistance due to resource limitations for both students and teachers (Bandalaria, 2020). Despite frequent class disruptions in the Philippines due to natural calamities (Save the Children Australia, 2013), the country was still caught off-guard during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the Philippines, the usual response to educational disruption was the conduct of make-up classes upon return to normalcy. Certainly, this was inapplicable to a protracted crisis such as this pandemic.

Moreover, several studies shed light into the Philippine experience of ERT from various angles. In a case study involving one Philippine teacher education institute, Cahapay (2020) reported the reshaping of assessments in response to the suspension of classes from an institutional perspective. He described it as a time of compromise between maintaining standards and quality in assessments with the logistical setbacks posed by

ERT. In a later phenomenological study, Cahapay (2021) wrote about the lived experiences of mothers in Mindanao who accompanied their grade school children through remote learning. He described the essence of their experiences as a conflict of spaces among home, work, and school. Nevertheless, the mothers showed resilience amidst the difficulties, as evident from the key terms that arose -- changes, challenges, adjustment, and adaptation, among others.

Continuing the focal theme of resilience, Jamon et al. (2021) conducted a phenomenological study involving secondary-level Filipino teachers. They lamented that being technologically literate did not equate to being equipped with the appropriate pedagogy in using technology to deliver teaching and learning experiences online. The teacher-respondents likewise echoed concerns on assessment given the difficulty in monitoring and providing feedback. They expressed skepticism on the authenticity of assessment and learning during this period. Despite the variety of challenges and difficulties they aired, they found the pandemic as an opportune time for professional development, especially in the arena of computer-aided teaching and materials development. Following the same reins, Robosa et al. (2021) shared similar results with their phenomenological research participated in by 10 Filipino public school teachers. Despite the stress and burnout they reported amidst the backdrop of heavy workload and inadequate resources, the experience allowed them to reflect on their profession and rekindle their passion in fulfilling their duty as teachers. Lastly, Alvarez (2020) revealed that financial and technological constraints had hindered college sophomores' access to learning during the pandemic. His phenomenological study also highlighted the greater need for psychosocial support during the pandemic as reported by the student-participants.

The aforementioned studies provided insight into the Philippine experience of ERT during the pandemic across various stakeholders. However, experiences specific to those of Filipino mathematics teachers remain uninvestigated as of writing. This serves as the impetus for the study, and at the same time, the knowledge gap that is aimed to be addressed.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study covered the experiences of three Filipino mathematics teachers as their institutions transitioned into fully online teaching during the first year of the pandemic. Its goal was to illustrate how ERT was implemented in the early months of the pandemic through the lived experiences of the three respondents. There was no intention to

evaluate the effectiveness of the teachers' responses to the challenges they faced. Likewise, this study did not intend to provide recommendations on how to improve online teaching. Further, while equity issues did surface in the discussions, particularly in relation to limited access to technology in some socioeconomic classes and sectors, addressing these issues was beyond the scope of this study.

Conceptual Framework

Ideas were adapted from the Anthropological Theory of the Didactic (ATD) by Chevallard (1986) in examining the narratives of the teachers in this paper. ATD is a theoretical offshoot of the Theory of Didactical Situations (TDS). As a program of research, it has been developing for the last thirty years or so, with a following in Europe, Canada, and some Latin American countries (Bosch & Gascón, 2014).

Within this theoretical lens is postulated that all human activities inhabit institutions (Bosch & Gascón, 2014). Furthermore, these activities can be conceived as praxeologies, consisting of a practical block and a theoretical block. The practical block can be divided into task-types, roughly described as the sort of things done in the activity, and techniques, or 'ways of doing' these task-types. Meanwhile, the theoretical block, are explanations referring to the practical block. It consists of technology, understood as that which answers the question of why a certain technique is valid to accomplish a certain task-type. A higher level in this theoretical block is called the theory, which is a discourse that underpins or justifies the technology. These four (task-types, techniques, technologies, and theories) are what makes up a praxeology (Chevallard, 2019).

The notion of praxeologies allows for the microscopic understanding of human actions, such as learning, or teaching. Each act can be taken individually, and then understood, within its proper institutional context. In a way, an ATD lens presupposes that the teaching and learning of mathematics are not only products of individual choices made by the teacher or the student. Instead, like any other human activity, the teaching of mathematics, and its learning, is also a product of the institutions where the activity happens (Bosch & Gascón, 2014). It must be stressed that these institutions are alive, and dynamic and at times maybe experiencing upheavals such as an unprecedented, and deadly pandemic. So, when a teacher, as in the cases found in this paper, makes certain decisions, and executes them in their classrooms during the COVID-19 lockdowns, ATD sees these decisions, and actions as products both of the individual, as well as the institution wherein that decision took place. While powerful and apt for use

in this phenomenological study, certain terminologies in the theory were purposely replaced by colloquial English equivalents to prevent an extensive introduction to ATD, which would be beyond the scope of this paper.

Education and its concomitant act of studying is essentially a social endeavor. Put in a more theoretically apt definition, studying is a system where a community of study, through the engagement of study-aides (i.e., primarily teacher or tutor), tries to come up with a valid answer to a question (Chevallard & Ladage, 2008). The mediation of the teacher in this study process and the collection of performances he does towards this end is termed in this paper as the *teaching act*. This study process has specific moments where teachers enact their role, producing observable and discrete actions (Bosch & Gascón, 2014). Schools and the classroom are primarily the loci of this communal act of studying.

Moreover, when a community of study embarks on the journey of education, gradually answering one question after another, an implicit process underlies this action. This process determines what type of questions students answer, and why they need to answer them. This is the process of the transposition of knowledge or termed *didactic transposition*. According to Chevallard and Bosch (2013), the mathematical knowledge subsisting in the community of mathematicians (i.e., experts' knowledge) is different from the mathematical knowledge that are written in textbooks and curricular documents (i.e., knowledge to be taught). This, in turn, is also different from the knowledge taught in the classroom (i.e., taught knowledge), and is finally different from the knowledge that is institutionalized by the student (i.e., learned knowledge). In didactic transposition, experts' mathematical knowledge is decontextualized, deliberated, and debated upon by the *noosphere* composed of people such as the producers of knowledge, government ministers, curriculum designers, heads of schools, teachers, among others (Bergsten et al., 2010). This is to usually come up with a curricular document that is practically a listing of what knowledge mathematics teachers ought to teach, when they will teach them, and how they will teach them. It is a foregone conclusion that this curricular document implies both the continuity and modality of the delivery of instruction (i.e., regular setup and schedule).

In summary, the present study borrows the ideas of *studying*, *teaching acts*, and *didactic transposition* from ATD (Chevallard, 1986). Given the interruption brought about by the contagion to the community of study (i.e., educational institutions and its stakeholders), the study views the ERT

responses of the institutions and teachers in coping with the pandemic as their teaching acts. Moreover, didactic transposition is adapted in its general sense, without regard to a particular mathematical body of knowledge; it is used in the present study to explore the delegation and implementation of curricular and pedagogical policies from institutions to teachers and from teachers to students.

Research Aim and Questions

The critical point during the abrupt transition into online teaching is an important phenomenon because of the uncertainties that lie ahead, especially in the case of Filipino mathematics teachers during the onset of the pandemic. This prompted an investigation towards the concurrent realities they faced. Thus, the paper aims to describe the experiences of three Filipino mathematics teachers during the pandemic through ideas borrowed from ATD: studying, teaching acts, and didactic transposition (Chevallard, 1986). By analyzing their narratives, it is hoped that sufficient contrast and texture can be provided to identify the challenges and opportunities they faced whilst ensuring continuity in the delivery of instruction through ERT amidst the pandemic.

Specifically, the paper responds to the following questions:

1. How did the schools of the three teachers respond to the crisis to ensure continuity in delivery of instruction? Consequently, how did the institutional response affect the teaching and learning of mathematics?
2. How did the three teachers experience the sudden migration into online modes of delivering instruction, particularly: (a) which key moments of the teaching act were altered, (b) what constraints were presented by these altered practices, and (c) how did they respond to these constraints?
3. How did these teachers view their unique experience of responding to an educational interruption? What insights did they gather about their own practice?

Indeed, one can view teaching experiences in this time of the pandemic as a trope on emergency response for which teachers have to be equipped in future similar disturbances (Hodges et al., 2020). However, more than just seeing an emergency response, this paper senses a comprehensive synopsis of things to come based on the abrupt migration to remote online teaching. The present study's significance lies in the researchers' attempts in possibly abstracting the challenges as well as the opportunities online education offers to an ever more digitizing world in the realm of mathematics education.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study utilized the phenomenological research design. A type of qualitative research design, phenomenology seeks to describe the lived experiences of individuals about a certain phenomenon as narrated by the research participants (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The resulting product of phenomenology is an essence of the experiences --- a two-fold composite description. Moustakas (1994) described these compositions as the textural description (i.e., what the participants have experienced), and the structural description (i.e., how the participants experienced the phenomenon). With respect to the present study, the phenomenon that was studied was the ERT of Filipino mathematics teachers. Phenomenology was appropriate for the present study because the goal was to describe the experiences of the three Filipino teacher-respondents in relation to their respective institutions' ERT responses and their individual coping mechanisms in the advent of the abrupt shift towards an online teaching-learning setting for mathematics.

Research Participants

The three respondents, Don, Jessica, and Stanley (not their real names) are co-authors of this paper and have personally experienced delivering ERT amidst the pandemic. They have consented to share their experiences premised under anonymity and confidentiality. In ensuring that their experiences do not bias the research findings, the respondents were not assigned to the working team that analyzed their own narratives. Moreover, they were not involved in generating the themes across the narratives. Nevertheless, these were presented to them, and they were given the opportunity to validate their narratives. Individual details about the teacher-respondents are presented in the Results section.

Data Collection

For phenomenological studies, conducting interviews is the common method of data collection (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). However, distancing measures imposed due to the pandemic necessitated data gathering to be conducted online. In lieu of online interviews conducted verbally, the researchers used Google Docs in consideration of the teacher-respondents' connectivity, availability, and convenience. An initial set of guide questions was given to the teacher-respondents during March 2020 that generally probed on the responses to the sudden shift to online teaching and learning. In turn, they uploaded their encoded narratives to a private folder provided by the researchers in Google Drive.

Subsequent follow-up questions and clarifications were then conducted within the document using the comments feature of Google Docs. Data collection took three weeks to complete. Some sample interview questions or probing statements are as follows:

1. How did your institution respond to school closures during the ECQ?
2. What were the challenges you encountered in conducting classes during ECQ? How did you respond to these?
3. What opportunities do you think arose during this time?

Data Analysis

The narratives of the three teachers were analyzed using content analysis (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017). This method was utilized not only to generate the significant themes that arise from the narratives, but also to determine the similarities and differences in their experiences and viewpoints. Using spreadsheet software, each narrative was thoroughly analyzed through coding meaning units in generating categories and emerging themes. This provided grounds for the overarching themes that respond to the descriptions aimed by phenomenology, and likewise capture the realities of the respondents during the pandemic. Lastly, the teacher-respondents were given the opportunity to validate their narratives. Table 1 shows a sample analysis conducted from meaning units to theme, as adapted from Erlingsson and Brysiewicz (2017).

Table 1. Sample Content Analysis from Meaning Unit to Higher Levels of Abstraction

Source	Don	Jessica	Stanley
Meaning Unit	"I heard no objections coming from any of the stakeholders."	"Their knowledge is just a shallow part of what the integral is."	"I think the teachers have the ability to transition to online learning."
Condensed Meaning Unit	No complaints from students or parents.	Students have a shallow understanding of the integral.	Teachers can move to online learning.
Code	Stakeholder reaction	Limitations in understanding	Ability to teach online
Category	Compliance of teachers and students.	Perceived effects of transition	Teacher's beliefs
Theme	A priori objects	The ERT may bring about learning gaps.	The ECQ and ERT as opportunities to reflect on what truly matters in education.

Describing the Three Cases

Don

Don, who has 15 years of teaching experience, is a mathematics teacher in a private school teaching senior high school students (Grade 11, ages 15-17). Their school follows a June through March school year; thus, the COVID-19 pandemic interruption

happened at the last fortnight of the school calendar. Don's school has an existing learning management system (LMS) that serves as a platform for online interaction between teachers and students. As the initial purpose of their LMS was to promote and encourage blended learning, he acknowledged that there was a lack of online teaching exposure for teachers and that the training in the use of LMS was inadequate.

In response to the government's school-closure orders, Don's school administrators ended the school year by suspending any type of classes physically or virtually. While students were allowed to communicate with the teachers via the LMS or electronic mail, no synchronous classes were conducted. His immediate supervisors encouraged the teachers in his department to send lecture notes but limited the number of graded tasks to two per subject. The components for grading students' performance were also reduced to written works and performance tasks. The fourth quarter examination, which was supposed to be a summative assessment of all the competencies achieved by the student in the course, had to be suspended. Teachers handling the same course had to eliminate some of the topics that were supposed to be taught according to their curriculum guides. Don lamented a possible consequence: his students would be under-prepared for the next subjects (e.g., Physics) since these rely on the prerequisite subject he taught (i.e., Integral Calculus).

Moreover, Don experienced the inconvenience of using the embedded tools in their LMS and the difficulty in creating authentic means to assess the students' learning. To him, assessments formed the backdrop for a feedback-loop between teacher and student. This feedback mechanism is essential so the teacher can properly scaffold the understanding of concepts by the students. Don's difficulties in the use of the LMS in checking outputs, putting marks, and providing feedback on the appropriate parts in the students' works made it impossible for the students to understand the mathematical errors in their output. Don believed that these comments or feedback could spark a meaningful mathematical discourse that would reveal the depth of the students' understanding of the concept. Nevertheless, Don saw the disruption as a form of encouragement to learn and maximize the use of their LMS and to experience using other media to deliver instruction. In addition, it made him see the value of creativity and flexibility in exploring ways to teach that go beyond the paper and the pen; more so, in seeing beyond the students' scores through compassion and understanding.

Jessica

Jessica, who also has 15 years of teaching experience, is a Grade 12 mathematics teacher in a private school that has experience in delivering blended teaching and learning prior to the pandemic (i.e., F2F for lectures, online for tasks and independent learning). This setup was called Alternative Learning and Teaching Opportunities (ALTO). Her school adopts a four-grading period academic calendar that runs from August to May. When the government ordered a month-long ECQ, the school conducted a quick survey to check how the teachers and the students were coping in the current online setup. With the results of this survey as the basis, a memorandum was crafted to introduce more policy modifications (e.g., reduced topics and graded formative assessments; final marks as passing or in progress). Holding synchronous online classes was the school's immediate action upon the government's order to halt physical classes. However, they later advised that synchronous discussions would no longer be implemented; rather, teachers should do their utmost in conducting asynchronous classes. To monitor the classes, teachers were advised to maximize the use of the school's LMS. In the first few days of the transition, Jessica attempted to mimic what she usually did in her offline classroom setup. However, she experienced inconveniences in using available hardware devices, such as the use of a trackpad and laptop to take control of the virtual blackboard to write mathematical symbols. Despite these setbacks, she still employed some changes in her teaching practice (e.g., incorporating exercise solutions in a slide presentation instead of writing them on the board). Inadequacy of training and lack of online teaching experience were revealed as Jessica and her colleagues tried to grapple with several problems and challenges that would continue to emerge.

Two problems that stood out in her lengthy account concerned dialogic feedback and authentic assessment of student learning. With only a few students taking the initiative to communicate with her during the lockdown, she found it difficult to monitor her students. Likewise, the scores that students got in the online tasks seemed to be an inaccurate reflection of their understanding of the lessons. A reason she cited was the availability of online applications, supporting gadgets, and other sources of assistance that students may have turned to in accomplishing their tasks without her knowing it. Jessica believed that the relaxing of policies, the entirety of experienced problems, and the undeniable unreadiness of the stakeholders on the sudden transition eventually resulted in some student learning gaps.

Nevertheless, Jessica had a positive outlook that with adequate support (e.g., educational technology specialists ready to assist), careful planning, proper implementation, right disposition, and appropriate attitudes, the virtual platform can mimic or even replace F2F, and go beyond, offering other affordances. According to her, the struggles they experienced provided the avenue to reflect on the knowledge and skills in Mathematics that are most essential. They gave her an opportunity to go back and revisit the skills that students must be able to develop from attending a Mathematics class (e.g., conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, strategic competence).

Stanley

Stanley, who has been teaching for ten years, is a junior high school (i.e., Grades 7 to 10, ages 12 to 15) mathematics teacher in one of a system of public charter schools across the Philippines. Similar to Jessica's school, his school follows the August-May school year, which is divided into four quarters. The interruption due to the pandemic in March 2020 occurred at the end of their third quarter. When strict quarantine measures were imposed, the institution administered an assessment survey on readiness and capability to both teachers and students. This survey aimed to gather data that would help the school move towards online learning; key decision-makers initially decided to push for online learning. Two weeks into the school closure, it became clear that the school would not be opening for an indefinite period of time. Thus, school leadership asked the teachers to submit implementation plans for the last five weeks of school and commit some amount of time during their work hours to set up online meetings with students and check for their well-being.

In planning for online learning, faculty members worked together to cope with the transition. Teachers who taught the same course selected topics and skills deemed fundamental and essential (i.e., sequences and series for Mathematics, and basic hypothesis testing for Statistics). They designed the content of the online materials for each week and discussed how the final term grades would be computed, with only online tasks and tests available to be possibly graded. However, by mid-April 2020, through a memorandum issued by the national body of Stanley's school system, all synchronous online classes were dropped and graded requirements were no longer sent to students. The third quarter grades were to be students' fourth quarter grades. Teachers continued to send materials online, but these were purely for students' self-study. In effect, their school year was prematurely closed. To offset the disrupted school

year, the school planned to open a bridging term in July 2020, during which students could work on tasks to improve their fourth quarter grade.

For Stanley, the disruption served as an opportunity to adapt to shifting needs and reflect on what truly matters in mathematics education. In the attempts of Stanley and his colleagues to migrate rapidly towards an online platform, the key take-away was the trimming of the intended syllabus to a minimum, aside from the concerns on effective instruction and assessment. On coping with the effects of the pandemic, he believed that quality mathematics teaching was still possible online, if teachers were given ample time to be trained on the appropriate approaches and be familiar with the features of chosen platforms. In addition, he thought that online teaching was advantageous towards providing feedback to students, especially to students who would not usually raise questions in F2F setup.

Results and Discussion

The analysis and discussion of the results are presented as three sections that not only highlight overarching themes across the three teachers' narratives, but also correspond to the research questions. Moreover, the discussions hereafter integrate both the textural and structural descriptions of their lived experiences from the ERT as a response of the institutions, to their coping strategies and challenges encountered and insights gained from the disruption.

Section 1: Institutional response — The birth pains of prematurely delivered online classes

From the experiences of the three Filipino mathematics teachers, online classes as the mode of ERT was chosen by their respective institutions amidst the pandemic's onset. Moreover, a finer look into their experiences of ERT reveal that the challenges their institutions faced can be broadly thematized as follows: *ad hoc solutions*, *technical challenges*, and *curricular reductions*.

Theme 1: Ad hoc solutions to an unprecedented disruption. All respondents reported that their schools did not have a well-established and detailed plan on how to respond to a long-term interruption brought about by a global contagion. Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, Philippine schools have been gradually integrating technologies that allow for some studying activity to occur in an online environment. In fact, in the cases of Don and Jessica, their respective schools have invested in this mode of instructional delivery by acquiring commercial LMS, whereas Stanley's school had no institutionalized LMS for use by the teachers

and students. It is evident from the narratives that all three schools resorted to online classes out of necessity, in response to the restrictions imposed by the government where physical, F2F classes were prohibited during ECQ. Moreover, there is a notable divergence among the experiences of the respondents regarding the migration to online mode of delivering instruction.

For instance, Stanley described the fluctuating responses of his school in different phases. The varying responses of his school involved the administration of an assessment survey on readiness and capability of online learning, changes in policies regarding the periodical exams, and petitions from teachers and students to suspend online learning for the rest of the school year. The initial responses (e.g., readiness survey) of his school were in effect due to the uncertainty posed by the pandemic, while the latter responses (e.g., suspension of online classes) were mainly influenced by the ECQ and its subsequent extensions. Eventually, his school system declared in April 2020 that online classes would not push through. On the other hand, Don commended his school for releasing guidelines pertinent to its course of action for the remaining two weeks of the school year, albeit posthaste --- a process which took the Principal's Council less than 24 hours to craft. He mentioned that with respect to the directives from the school administration, he "heard no objections coming from any of the stakeholders." Don's school migrated to a fully online set-up too, maximizing the use of the commercial LMS acquired by the school prior to the pandemic.

However, among the three, only Jessica was able to experience simulating her classes online --- leading a community of study in an online environment according to the school's mandate. In her case, she expressed her sentiment on what seemed to be a lapse on the part of her school's administrators, highlighting a need for clearer guidelines regarding the continuation of learning via online medium:

"... I think the administrators should have first given the constituents (parents, teachers and students) a write-up of how online learning works, what is expected of them, how this is done, what benefits can be obtained if we continue online learning, why we need to do this, etc."

It must be noted that the Philippine educational system is no stranger to interruptions, as the Philippines experiences suspensions of classes on a regular basis due to recurring typhoons that threaten parts of the country the whole year round

(Cadag et al., 2017). Disruptions caused by factors that threaten human safety leave schools no choice but to cease operations. Whenever natural calamities reach devastating levels, schools become unavailable for educational use as they are automatically converted into temporary shelters or evacuation centers (Asia Pacific Coalition for School Safety, 2017). The pandemic, unlike natural calamities, not only hampered the delivery of basic goods and services but also reduced living conditions significantly --- a scenario that will most likely linger for an indefinite amount of time. Moreover, situations that endanger human life render the continuation of educational activity pointless. Even if Filipinos seemed to have developed a sense of resilience from a constant exposure with calamities (Bracamonte, 2015), the interruption brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic proved to be like no other. Its end is out of sight, yet educational institutions are expected to ensure a continuing delivery of education notwithstanding that F2F classes are highly prohibited. Due to the said restriction, teachers and students involuntarily submit themselves to the inevitable reality of conducting and participating in online classes. The pandemic not only exposed the unpreparedness of the country for such a transition, but also widened already existing disparities between students with different socio-economic backgrounds (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2020). On this matter, Jessica opined:

“Even before the pandemic, there was no equity of resources among public schools and among private schools. Some schools are better equipped than others with regards to facilities, opportunities and resources. Teachers in public and private are not trained and certified for online learning classes.”

Numbers from the PISA-2018 database indicate that no fewer than 60% of students in the Philippines do not have access to computers at home that can be dedicated for schoolwork, and more than 50% of Filipino students do not have access to the internet (OECD, 2020). In relation, Alvarez (2020) reported how financial and technological constraints have hampered Filipino students' access to education during the pandemic. Hence, it is reasonable to say that in terms of the required facilities for online learning, Filipino schoolchildren lack the capability to transition to online learning --- and this unreadiness poses a major consideration for any decision related to continuing educational activity amidst the disruption.

Theme 2: Technical challenges sprouting from the institutional mandate.

When teachers re-organize mathematical knowledge in the classroom and create the necessary situation for education, this is affected by the work or activities he does outside the classroom (Miyakawa & Winsløw, 2013). These activities may include teacher-training, observation of other teachers' classes, reading through another teacher's lesson plan, and even conversations over coffee at faculty lounges. All three subjects in this study expressed their wish for a training before being put out to wade into the waters of online teaching. Quoting Stanley, “My suggestion for the next SY is that teachers be given training on how to conduct online classes. By that time, an online learning platform should have been chosen.” For Don and Jessica, whose schools specifically invested in a commercial LMS, they were exposed to some form of institutionally mandated training. Despite these, they claimed that these were insufficient, echoing that technological literacy and apt pedagogies do not automatically come hand-in-hand (Jamon et al., 2021):

Don: “Training sessions were just given for a couple of hours in the past summer in-service training (I think that was two summers ago) and sometime in the middle of last school year. Yes [there was training], but may not be enough. I think 3 or 4 short sessions. We were not given, say, a pamphlet of guidelines on how to use the features of LMS. It could have helped us remember the things we learned in the sessions.”

Jessica: “The school provided training and workshops on the use of LMS. There are even workshops that all teachers and students are required to attend... It is easy to say that we can teach the content. We are not sure that it was delivered effectively to the students. I am not equipped with the knowledge of the different strategies in teaching mathematics in an online setting.”

It can also be possibly seen that even though the school has necessary tools (e.g., LMS) for online learning and has provided training for teachers, the Philippine educational system, at large, is still a novice in online learning. The teachers are open to migrating towards the online platform; however, there are still some hesitations to deviate from what is supposed to be normal, i.e., F2F discussion in a regular classroom. Teachers are clinging to the comfort of the traditional set-up and looking for those features in the virtual platform (Cahapay,

2020). The respondents were quoted indicative of such:

Don: *"It's easier to check a tangible (actual) output than something that was just uploaded in our LMS. While our LMS has those features/tools to allow placing of comments and marks on the uploaded student output, it's more difficult... It took me then [a] large amount of time to finish checking my students' outputs."*

Jessica: *"...on the first day of our online class, I tried to mimic what I always do in the classroom. However, writing mathematical symbols or illustrating the diagram of the problem on the white board screen of the laptop using a trackpad is a bit off. So, I realized that I cannot do the same ways that I do in our regular F2F classes on the online platform."*

Unreadiness in terms of capabilities to conduct online learning was exposed as well, primarily with the teachers' inadequate experience and know-how in the use of LMS. The following quotes back up this claim:

Don: *"There were teachers who didn't know (or struggled) how to use our LMS... There's actually a feature in our LMS that will allow us to do that [conduct synchronous online classes] but I guess we don't know how to use [it] because we never got the chance to use it."*

Jessica: *"Some of my colleagues are not using the LMS. Everyone has an account, but some do not use it at all. They find it difficult shifting from the traditional set-up to the online set-up because they do not even know how to upload a file, create a session for the [LMS brand], or add content in the LMS."*

Moreover, it's not just the use of LMS that the respondents are concerned with. Jessica, who at that time learned that her school will be conducting online classes for the rest of the school year, seemed to be daunted by the fact that she lacked the necessary equipment for online classes in addition to her inadequate skills in the use of online learning platforms:

"I do not have available teaching and learning materials, hardware devices (reliable microphone, camera, pen for tablet,

etc.) and other software applications which can be used during online classes."

Theme 3: Curricular reductions, thematic autism, and its consequences. At the start of the school year, the predetermined knowledge intended to be taught is set for implementation, and this process shall be evaluated when the school year ends. An interruption such as school-closures brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic represents a rupture in the integrity of the body of knowledge-to-be-taught present in curricular documents. The resolution of this interruption is not as easy as making the noosphere reconstruct the knowledge-to-be-taught in an instant. What ensued in the examined narratives was that school leadership made posthaste decisions about the curricula. This was with respect to balancing the remaining days in the school calendar with that of the stakeholders' situations (e.g., access to technology, socioemotional well-being), and exhibiting compassion toward their students. These can be gleaned from the following statements:

Don: *"Since face-to-face lectures were suspended and we can't do it using the online platform as well, we failed to reach a significant number of learning objectives... Our academic coordinator appealed to us in the STEM Department to limit our online tasks to just two, so as not to burden our students... [who] will be doing a lot of online tasks, I was discouraged [by the school] to send more lecture notes for them to study on their own."*

Jessica: *"...the administration of the [school] asked each [specialization] strand to prioritize the topics that should be given during online classes. So, the Basic Calculus Team chose the topics that can be discussed by all the teachers given the time constraint and the existing conditions, and the capacity of the students to understand the topic on their own... So, we resorted to cutting down some of the topics for the fourth quarter so that students would not be studying too many concepts on their own... The topics were reduced and simplified [so] that students can easily understand on their own using the learning materials that we provided [for the asynchronous classes]."*

Stanley: *"The grade for 3rd quarter will be given as it is, since giving requirements during the ECQ will add up to the anxiety of students... Teachers are not expected to cover*

all of the remaining topics for the rest of the school year; only up to 80% of the intended curriculum. They are given the prerogative to identify which of the topics are essential and must be included in the remaining five weeks of the SY... [thus,] we identified the topics that the students won't probably need."

In other words, the institutions granted teachers (either in groups or individually) the autonomy of curtailing topics from the syllabus which they deemed unessential. But doing so placed teachers in difficult positions. Chevallard's (2002) thematic confinement or thematic autism can perhaps explain why this is the case: teachers are confined to organizing bits and pieces of knowledge around certain themes. Decisions about organizing them at higher levels, such as the level of the school or even that of society, are out of their control (Barbé et al., 2005). Hence, it would be understandable if Jessica became disappointed when she said that "the sudden shift to online learning disrupted the whole system that was plotted at the start of the semester." This is because the plotted system was put in place not only considering the course of action for a year, but with the entire K-12 curriculum in mind. The inability of the noosphere to reorganize knowledge-to-be-taught during times of abrupt educational interruption and the futile attempt of teachers to assume the function for which they are least equipped results in a delivery of instruction that is fragmented, and which lies far from the original intent and design of the curriculum. Hence, in the case of Don whose school canceled online lectures and only gave students two tasks, he was quoted echoing the possible aftereffects of such haphazard yet inevitable mandate:

"Good thing we were able to cover the calculus lessons needed for their Grade 12 General Physics next year. But for those who will be taking courses in college that will require background in basic calculus, professors should not assume that the students were taught all the topics/competencies in the senior high basic calculus."

Furthermore, a meta-analytic study by Cooper et al. (1996) concluded that for every two months of educational discontinuity brought about by summer vacations, about a month's worth of lessons are lost by way of an achievement test. The effects are worse for mathematics compared to reading, and most detrimental to skills such as mathematical computation and spelling. No wonder echoes of this were heard from the teacher-respondents. For

example, Don worried about his students not being able to appreciate the reason for studying anti-differentiation rules because they were only given a "a shallow picture...of what integration is" and it "might lead to integration as nothing but a set of rules." Similarly, Stanley fretted that students might not be able to properly understand hypothesis testing which is needed for research subjects in the succeeding years, and that "the future research advisers of this batch will have a hard time since the foundation of these students in hypothesis testing is affected [by the adjustments due to the disruption]."

Hence, transitioning the delivery of instruction from F2F to online modes first and foremost requires a re-thinking of the knowledge-to-be-taught. It necessitates a re-negotiation by stakeholders or aptly termed the noosphere. Prematurely giving birth to online classes no matter how it is framed as out of dire need, as in our cases, will be fraught with problems.

In summary, the plight of the respondents reflects their unreadiness towards the move to online learning, which in turn, reflects their respective institutions' unreadiness as well. These are manifested by the lack of technical skills in using institutionally acquired learning platforms and lack of baseline infrastructure. The general unreadiness that stretches across the institutions gave rise to a secondary set of challenges namely, apprehensions on which mathematics topics to cut because of mandates to curtail the syllabus, reorganizing the grading systems, and the real possibility of shortchanging students' learning of skills that are prerequisites for higher mathematics. The unanticipated fissures became gaps that should be bridged --- gaps that require continuously evolving responses, consisting of well-thought courses of actions that address the impending short-term concerns arising from time to time.

Section 2: Teachers' response — Altered teaching acts in the digital mathematics classroom

Delving into the teachers' experiences of teaching online amidst the ECQ, two key moments of the teaching act were found to be altered: *communication* and *assessment*. These are further explored in the discussions that follow for each theme.

Theme 1: Issues on communication and discourse. The narratives in this study also demonstrated microscopic level problems relating to the activities within the classroom. For Don and Jessica, one of the most pressing issues they faced was keeping informed of how their students were doing --- the problem of communication between the teacher and student. Quoting each:

Don: *"I was able to fix a schedule to accommodate inquiries via [email service provider] and our LMS. I even used my [social media account] because there were times that I found it easier to communicate with them as a class via their group chat... While I welcomed inquiries via email or via our LMS, only few communicated with me... Seeing students' actual behavior and gestures during a face-to-face lecture would help the teachers gauge whether their students are just doing well or not, coping well or not with the pacing of the discussion, etc."*

Jessica: *"...I tried to connect with the students and engage them in a discussion; however, only a few would respond... It is not easy to get feedback from the students of how they are coping with self-paced learning. You have to wait for the students to initiate inquiries regarding their learning experiences and hardships in the performance of tasks or understanding the concepts... So, there is indeed a big educational gap between the teacher and the students because of communication."*

In the very simple definition of studying, notice that both the community of study and the teacher engage in some form of dialogue where a question is raised, and the students must at least attempt at giving an answer. This dynamic becomes reasonably problematic when the dialogue is brought into an online environment. First, the act of posing the question loses its almost exclusively oral character (Chevallard, 2008), because and as it very often happens in online classes, the questions are textualized, existing in presentation slides or in task sheets, etc. Many of the nuances that can only be found in a talking-moving person are lost. This textualization of the question has in fact become the norm in the schools of both Don and Stanley. While no longer offering online classes, they nonetheless sent materials for the self-study of students.

Secondly, the subsequent act of attempting to give an answer to the question posed can be delayed (Chevallard, 2008), as in cases of asynchronous classes. In such cases, opportunities are lost whereby the teacher can dynamically interact with the student and, in the process, help him to arrive at a valid answer. All three respondents reminisced about the ease of providing helpful remarks or comments at opportune moments in the F2F classroom, and were quoted as follows:

Don: *"You can't compare the ease of calling a student who wants to ask a question or clarify something in a face-to-face environment to that of an online platform where you have to check (as frequently as possible) a lot of small buttons or tools to do just that... The disadvantage of asynchronous [classes] is on the communication between the teacher and his/her students. I may not be able to entertain their questions and clarifications right away."*

Jessica: *"I can roam around to see how they are doing the problem. After they have solved the problems on their seats, sometimes, I would ask volunteers to explain to the whole class their solution. It is also easier to spot students who are confused or those who are doing other things. So, I can call their attention and inquire what their thoughts are."*

Stanley: *"For me the most challenging part is how to monitor student progress while conducting the online class. In the status quo, I usually go around the classroom to check if each student is on task during the administration of drills and exercises, and randomly check students' solutions to see if they understood the lesson. I'm not sure how this will be done online."*

This to them was a didactic act that was lost as teachers moved their classes online. Moreover, even when the teacher opts to hold synchronous classes, the dynamics among the community of study are still significantly diminished because their interaction with each other is severely limited. The space-time dilation of a once-seamlessly connected chain of events is perhaps the most characteristic difference between F2F and online modes of teaching. Posing the question by the teacher and that of the answering by the student within the same physical space and time may no longer be possible.

On a final note in this section, the role of the teacher is explored. Within the definition of studying, the role of teachers subsists within the category study-aid. In very traditional didactic systems, this role is significantly large, and it would even appear that the teacher has already fixed everything, leaving very little for students to do (Chevallard, 2008). Moving the classroom to an online environment brings to many teachers a tectonic shift in role. Due to the apparent distortion in space-time and the constraints it brings to online interactions, teachers must relinquish much of their control of the study system to the other participants

--- the students. "They [teachers] have to put their trust in the students that they will study the lessons independently and responsibly...", as Jessica pointed out poignantly in her narrative. Adequate re-organization of the classroom experience is called to respond to this monumental shift, both on the part of the teachers and the students also.

Theme 2: Assessment in transition, the feedback loop, and its validity. All the teachers in this research took particular interest in assessments and the difficulty with which they encountered this in their experience of educational interruption and transition into online teaching. The experiences of the teachers with respect to assessment may be divided into two: first, viewing formative assessment as a route to conceptual understanding; second, questioning the validity of summative assessments.

Regarding the first facet of assessment as deduced from the teachers' experiences, for Don, assessments were an essential part of a feedback loop between teacher and student. This feedback loop creates the space necessary for teachers to scaffold the understanding of the students, using the language of Vygotsky: "Scaffolding helps in the students' learning of math. Feedback is helpful in the whole process of scaffolding. So it's really important that feedback is being given [at] the soonest possible [time]." However, the abrupt interruption and their school's instruction to limit the giving of assessments-tasks to students diminished this function of assessments. They were advised to give at most two tasks, and they came in the form of an alternative type of assessment called performance tasks. Each task is not progressive in a sense that all the teachers had to do was give out a set of instructions, then wait for the student to comply at an agreed date and time. Though no fault of his own, he ended up becoming merely someone who would send instructions and then collect the output, give a mark, and return the marked paper to the student. To the lost opportunity for further scaffolding through more formative assessments, Don reacted:

"...we could have given exercises that would challenge students to go beyond the use of their algorithmic reasoning. We could have prepared something that will not simply require the students to apply the rules of integration... Because feedback was not made on the students' outputs, the students wouldn't know why they received such grades/scores."

Similar to Don, Jessica echoed a tangential perspective. Reflective of the difficulty with which

Jessica was delivering instruction online through her asynchronous classes, she opined:

"...the delivery of the lesson would have been more effective if students were sending feedback to the teachers of how they are coping with the practice exercises that they are working on so that teachers can also identify the needed mathematical competencies of the students... It is difficult to assess learning in the online setting whether synchronous or asynchronous. It was difficult to pinpoint who among my students are having difficulty understanding the concepts."

More so, her assessments gravitated towards simple tasks such as taking the indefinite integral of a function. She could not assess what she termed as conceptual understanding of the tasks she was teaching because at the outset, her online classes limited her from developing these understandings. This was a result of a departmental decision to trim the syllabus and focus on essential skills, in consideration of her colleagues and students' adjustment with the online setup. However, she expressed regret on this matter, but ultimately had no choice due to the surrounding circumstances:

"...in order for mathematics to have meaning to the students, I think I should have provided tasks that would make them think and make connections to the concepts and not merely focus on the procedural part... [in the quarterly assessment] we were not able to assess students' procedural skills in mathematics ([since] they can use online calculators) ... We were not able to give more application problems that would test their understanding of the concepts because we were limited to discussing only the parts which are procedural in nature."

Meanwhile, the second view of assessment as experienced by the teachers revolved around concerns on its validity. For Stanley, whose school abandoned the idea of holding online classes, and instead just prescribed teachers to regularly send self-study materials, assessment was left to the initiatives of the students to check for their own learning. However, he echoed thoughts on the validity of assessment that resonated with that of Jessica:

"Students' solutions may not be reflective of their true abilities since they are exposed to the use of the Internet and the teacher

cannot control what they see or browse on the Internet. They may be using online calculators and pretend to solve during the online classes."

For Jessica, who among the three spent the most time in the online set-up, assessment practice meant simulating what would have happened in the classroom had they stayed in an offline format. There was still a regular stream of exercises or drills, weekly quizzes, and summative tests. Highlighting Jessica's assessment beliefs: "Since mathematics is a skill subject, the role of practice in enhancing their procedural fluency in solving mathematics problems is important." Although Jessica might have had the opportunity to simulate assessment practices in an offline classroom, the very nature of the online environment constrained her from achieving the goals of an assessment. She would eventually declare that there was no way of telling whether the students were learning. When they took their quizzes, there was no way for her to know whether the student used some software, applet, or even asked their classmate for the correct answer. She was quoted:

"...we cannot ensure that our students are really the one's answering the examinations/activities/tasks... Getting high scores in the tasks/tests doesn't mean that students have a full understanding of the topic. Before the ECQ, I had already identified some students who really need close supervision even on simple computational tasks. They had a hard time understanding concepts even if we discussed it face-to-face and we still conducted consultations during vacant hours. But, in the online [classes], suddenly they were able to answer all the activities correctly... Some of my colleagues who are using [software] found that some students were using the same IP address when answering the exam. The students admitted that some of them are asking their classmates who have stable connections to answer the exam for them."

Moreover, technical aspects of the online environment prohibited the teachers from replicating teaching acts that are helpful to achieve the goals of an assessment. Such was in the case of Don who struggled to put annotations and comments on his students' work right where they were needed: "...it's not easy to mark and to put comments on the [students'] work even if our LMS have tools to do such things. It's easier to have actual outputs and use a pen to put some comments on

them." Meanwhile, Jessica could not impose a timed drill because not all students have reliable internet access: "Some do not have a stable connection at home. Some used mobile data, so it might be costly, and it might not provide a good connection." Indeed, just like the migration of classes, moving assessments into online environments presented these teachers several challenges, many of which are especially difficult but essential to the study process.

Evaluation in the classroom is part of instructional design, as it goes hand-in-hand with how the students are supposed to reconstruct the knowledge that was taught to them (Barbé et al., 2005; Chevallard, 1999). Thus, when the system was interrupted and the school and teachers scrambled to modify instructional design to fit within the online mode of delivery, the original assessment strategy broke down. Arising from such a dilemma is the compromise between curricular standards and quality assessments (Cahapay, 2020), which resulted in skepticism posed by teachers on the authenticity of assessment, since the feedback loop suffered from monitoring difficulties (Jamon et al., 2021). Hence, it is to no surprise that Jessica questioned whether their compromise between mathematics content, assessment, and the constraints of the digital setup truly led to actual student learning. More so, Don lamented the lost opportunity to administer his final examination, or his concern that students were no longer able to improve their scores with successive tests or exercises because there was none to speak of: "So those who were not doing well... did not get the chance to improve their overall grading period performance with the Final Examination anymore." Truly, whatever palliative assessment strategy teachers may come up with will end up being problematic.

Section 3: Silver lining — seeing opportunities in this time of crisis

The continuous delivery of teaching and learning during the onset of the pandemic showed that education is not a lost cause amidst such uncertain times. In this last section, the experiences of the three teacher-respondents show that the ERT accorded them two opportunities: *a space for reflection* and *discovering online teaching*. The first theme discusses how the pandemic and school closures inadvertently made them reflect on what is truly essential in mathematics education. On the other hand, the second theme presents the hope and opportunities the teacher-respondents found in the online teaching-learning setup.

Theme 1: A space for reflection on what really matters in mathematics teaching. The abrupt transition of classrooms into online environments required the teachers in this research to look hard and think deeply about their practice (Robosa et al., 2021), with Stanley expressing, *“It makes me rethink as to what the important aspects of education really are.”*

First, they grappled with the question pertaining to curricula like determining which topics were important and which can be left out. These resulted from institutional mandates and had already been treated elsewhere in this paper. Second, they had to confront their changing roles in the classroom dynamic. From someone who purposely poses questions leading to a predetermined organization of knowledge, now they can merely suggest questions into an organization of knowledge that may not be clearly defined just yet. This could be seen from the discussion on their altered teaching acts. It must be remarked that this transition is far from over, and not the least fought with resistance.

Finally, the situation gave the teachers a chance to give a hard look at the nature of the subject they are teaching --- in this case, mathematics. Their narratives were rife with expressions of epistemological beliefs as can be seen in the following selected quotes. Don wrote, *“Math is said to build on itself...one can’t move to the next Math lesson or survive it if the pre-requisites are not learned well.”* On the other hand, Jessica expressed:

“In learning mathematics, students should not only be able to perform procedural knowledge in solving problems, but they should also be able to reason mathematically and make sense of mathematical problems... When students have a clear understanding of the concepts, then they can use or recreate the appropriate algorithm for any mathematical problem... [students are able to show] how it is being used in real-life situations.”

The sequential nature of mathematics learning content can be seen from Don’s statement. Meanwhile, with Jessica viewing mathematics as a subject filled with skills (i.e., procedural, conceptual, applicational), the meaningful understanding of mathematics goes beyond doing the correct procedure, and that real-life applications are of importance. Whether these ruminations can be brought to their proper conclusion and bear fruit in a renewed teaching practice truly depends on how these teachers are supported in their transition.

Theme 2: Discovering online teaching.

Throughout human history, necessity remains to be the mother of invention (Kelman, 2006). The unprecedented interruption brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent closure of physical schools created the need for teachers to become more creative in their craft. Jessica, for instance, admitted, *“Before the ECQ, I used [proprietary LMS] only when uploading learning materials, creating announcements, creating folders for online submissions of activities, or recording of students’ grades and attendance.”* Likewise, Stanley similarly shared,

“Before ECQ, I have used online learning platforms...primarily to upload supplementary resources such as additional practice worksheets. I also used these to communicate to students by reiterating announcements already made in class and reminding them of important schedules such as deadlines of project submissions.”

However, during the pandemic, that portal had become the classroom and along with that change, they had to learn new skills necessary in this new classroom while coping with institutional mandates (e.g., cutting of syllabus, limiting of assessments). Don similarly claimed that he *“started using other means like creating a video and uploading it in our LMS.”*

The teacher-respondents showed that the modifications in their teaching acts were nothing more than a necessary endeavor and were barely a fulfillment of a teacher’s duty which is similar to the phenomenological essence found by Robosa et al. (2021). In the wide gamut of issues and challenges they faced in transitioning to online learning, they have not forgotten that ultimately all their labors were because they want, and society expects them, to continuously provide education. As Jessica wrote, teachers *“opted to continue facilitating student learning despite the challenges and limitations...in a remote setting.”* Even in the cases of Don and Stanley who no longer held online classes, they kept on sending materials to their students. These actions reveal the respondents’ innate flexibility in adapting to the rapid nature of their transition to fully online teaching, which emerges as an important trait now required of teachers who are in the same plight (Jamon et al., 2021). In addition, the narratives showed that despite the challenges they experienced, the respondents were hopeful for quality online teaching. Stanley opined that *“teachers have the ability to transition to online learning,”* and what was necessary was ensuring that both teachers and students were *“well-equipped in*

conducting online classes.” Likewise, Jessica reiterated that quality teaching and assessment could work provided “the students and teachers have the right disposition regarding online learning” as supported by the institution and its administrators. In addition, Don expressed a positive reflection of his experience and development: *“There’s this motivation to explore technology per se and see how it can help you expand your repertoire of instructional techniques and refine your teaching practices.”*

As had been noted by McKee (2020), prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, online education was commonly viewed as merely supplementary. School closures brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic changed this view; now, online education has become the principal pathway to studying. Along with that tectonic shift, teachers like the ones in this research are more and more discovering ways on how to bring their classroom practice into the online world. At the dawn of the new yet uncertain future, Don, Jessica, and Stanley have in a way responded to the unusual challenges in perhaps the most possible and convenient ways they could avail for themselves. The teachers followed the institutional mandates (e.g., reduction of learning activities in the case of Don) to the best of their ability, weigh in on the curricular contents and prioritize to cover what seemed to be the more essential ones (e.g., teachers were only expected to cover up to 80% of the intended curriculum in Stanley’s case), and take note of the needs in online teaching (e.g., the necessary equipment and other learning materials as expressed by Jessica) that they can surely raise in their respective learning communities in preparation for the new school year.

Conclusion

To some extent, this paper laid out some form of groundwork for research-based contingency plans that stakeholders (i.e., administrators, educators, and government officials) may consider drafting given the challenges and opportunities that come with ERT for any similar situations that may arise in the future. In this regard, below are some points for recommendation that may be considered, divided into five areas:

1. Communication: Thorough consultation with other stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and students, must be observed to ensure proper logistics and clear communication channels of directives regarding school-level decisions.
2. Curriculum: Modifications in the curriculum may be discussed among teachers so that adjustments can be made in terms of

content knowledge, conceptual difficulty, intended goals, and methods of instruction.

3. Infrastructure: Provision for the acquisition of necessary learning materials and equipment is needed to help deliver instruction, along with the appropriate training for teachers and students on how to use them.
4. Instruction: Exploration of blended learning models to be followed (e.g., flipped classroom) can help teachers and students cover the prescribed competencies.
5. Equity: Planning for the future should consider fair access to resources so that ideally, no school, teacher, and student are left behind.

Despite any teacher’s desire to be flexible enough to adapt to online teaching, this desire may be countered with situations that limit their flexibility such as what had been observed in the study via didactic transposition. What had been established early on, be it the curriculum or syllabus, is difficult to revise especially for teachers who were not involved in the design process. Moreover, haphazard redaction of curricular content during ERT may be problematic for building up future competencies.

Hence, through the narratives of the three Filipino mathematics teachers, the present phenomenological research described their experiences on the educational disruption brought about by the pandemic. It viewed the community of study being disrupted, thus giving rise to altered teaching acts and some limitations as interpreted from the didactic transposition. The very essence of the phenomenon, as derived from the experiences of the teacher-respondents, is that the online ERT, while challenging due to treading into an unfamiliar setting for both institutions and their teachers, brought about opportunities to adapt and reflect on what truly matters in mathematics education.

The general response of institutions was to migrate to online instruction, albeit with varying outcomes. Stanley’s school attempted to but suspended the transition to online learning. Don’s institution did migrate but on a very limited basis. Finally, there was Jessica who had extensive experience with the shift to online teaching and learning. This path of migrating to online environments is not rid of obstacles, as can be seen from the overarching theme of unreadiness. There are key curricular decisions that require the attention of the wider community and for which neither teachers nor institutions alone can address. This became evident in the reduction of the mathematics syllabus, wherein it could be seen as an attempt to redesign, albeit in the shortest amount of

time possible, a product of didactic transposition that had been planned early on.

During the transfer of the classroom practice into online environments, the key moments of the teaching act that changed are the following: posing questions and eliciting responses in class and assessing student learning. Moreover, teachers were limited from elaborating the theoretical environment of the mathematical tasks they gave due to their unfamiliarity with the online classroom. In response to these changes, teachers holding online classes attempted to communicate with students, restricted the mathematics competencies, and abridged the assessment strategies to a bare minimum. The move to an online environment exposed several issues, such as the altered space-time, heavy textualization of concepts, the non-responsiveness of students, and questions on authenticity of assessment practices. These concerns need a thorough appreciation and response in future initiatives to migrate teaching into online modalities.

The crisis that the teachers and schools faced worldwide presented both challenges and opportunities for mathematics teachers. The greatest of the challenges perhaps was carrying out vital tasks that were crucial to the transition to online learning, thereby ensuring continuity in learning and effectiveness of online instructional delivery. However, one cannot deny that the pandemic changed the perspective of teachers regarding education, learning, and the nature of mathematics. It also left the teachers no choice but to change their ways and acquire new skills to adapt to the evolving educational landscape. Teachers were reminded that the move to online learning necessitates a deep and constant reflection about what is essential; in facing the challenges, we move forward together as one community of stakeholders. Despite the bleak future ahead, the pandemic gave us a reason to look forward to the future with hope – one where teaching mathematics now transcends borders and points in time.

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